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Healing Frames. Health Histories beyond 'West' and 'East' through the Lens of Cinema¹

Abstract: *The text is a review of "A Critical History of Health Film in Central Eastern Europe and Beyond" by Victoria Shmidt and Karl Kaser – a significant scholarly work that offers an in-depth examination of health films and their role in shaping public health perceptions and policies in Central and Eastern Europe. Drawing on extensive archival material, this interdisciplinary book bridges the fields of film history, media studies, social history, public health history and Central Eastern European studies, providing readers with a nuanced understanding of how visual media was used to promote health issues. The book covers a broad temporal scope, encompassing case studies from the interwar period, World War II, the socialist era, and the post-socialist transformation.*

Keywords: *Health Films; Health Policies; Health Discourses; Filmmakers; Europe; USA; National and International Organisations.*

**A CRITICAL HISTORY OF
HEALTH FILMS IN CENTRAL
AND EASTERN EUROPE AND
BEYOND**

Victoria Shmidt and Karl Kaser

Victoria Shmidt, Karl Kaser (2023) A Critical History of Health Films in Central and Eastern Europe and Beyond. Routledge. ISBN 9781032215143, 284 Pages 35 B/W Illustrations

It is an honour to review the monograph authored by Victoria Shmidt and Karl Kaser. For me, as a historian and ethnologist/anthropologist with interests in visual studies and medical anthropology, the book is not only fascinating, but highly valuable, as the authors develop a new, multilayered ap-

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proach to the history of Central and Eastern Europe through the lens of health films.

The historical presence of health films in Central and Eastern Europe is beyond question, but despite their preserved legacy, the films' history remains a widely unexplored topic to this day. Shmidt and Kaser's book changes this. This interdisciplinary book bridges the fields of film history, public health, and Central and Eastern European studies, providing readers with a nuanced understanding of health films and their role in shaping public health perceptions and policies in Central and Eastern Europe.

Both authors are well-known and established scholars with profound knowledge of the region: Karl Kaser's 'model thinking' meets Victoria Shmidt's attention to detail in a fruitful combination. The applied cross-national historical comparative analysis differentiates the driving political forces in producing and disseminating health films, contributes to the contextualization of health films, and highlights their active, agentic position. Following Juan Fernandez's approach of "grouping singular events under complex interpretative concepts" and focusing on a "rhizome narrative", Shmidt and Kaser use mainly films from Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia, analyzing them in a broad temporal scope, encompassing the interwar period, World War II, the socialist era, and the post-socialist transformation. The justification for the particular focus on health films from these two states is based on several compelling reasons: Both Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia were regional pioneers in the use of film as a medium for public health education. Czechoslovak and Yugoslav filmmakers were known for their innovative approaches to film production, which significantly influenced the genre of health films. These countries often led the way in adopting new technologies and narrative techniques that made their health films particularly effective. The political and social contexts of Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia provided interesting case studies for how health films were used as tools of state policy and social engineering. The shifting political landscape of Czechoslovakia, from a democratic interwar period to Nazi occupation and then to socialism, provided diverse contexts in which health films were produced and utilized. The specific emphasis of the Yugoslav socialist regime on collective health and education, coupled with the country's ethnic diversity, presented a distinct environment for the production of health films aimed at fostering a unified public health consciousness.

One of the book's strengths lies in the detailed archival research. The extensive archival materials and the availability of well-documented

records in Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia allowed for an in-depth analysis of the production, distribution, and reception of health films. The authors did access a wealth of archival footage, government documents, and contemporary critique, enabling them to construct a comprehensive history of health films in these countries.

By emphasizing Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia, Shmidt and Kaser provide a detailed and representative study of how health films developed and operated within the broader context of Central and Eastern Europe, but also within a global context. Shmidt and Kaser organize the films into "assemblages" to illustrate the interconnectedness of local and global influences on health film production. The authors illustrate how health films in Central and Eastern Europe were influenced by and contributed to global trends through transnational collaborations and exchanges. International organizations like the Red Cross, the International Institute for Intellectual Cooperation and its subdivision the International Educational Cinematographic Institute, the Rockefeller Foundation, the World Health Organization, etc. played a significant role in fostering international collaboration, but also in shaping the content and the production of health films. The distribution and dissemination of health films also had a significant international dimension. Health films were screened in various international settings, reaching diverse audiences and contributing to the global discourse on public health. These films were not just local educational tools but were embedded in global health movements and ideologies. In the interconnected global world there were (and are) important hierarchies. It is to the authors' credit that they point out power relations and asymmetrical power dynamics within the global context. The book discusses how health films from Western Europe and the United States often set the standards for film production and public health messaging. Filmmakers in Central and Eastern Europe frequently had to conform to these standards in order to gain international recognition and funding. Western countries typically had more resources for producing high-quality films, leading to a dependency on their techniques and narratives. This created a hierarchy where Western models were seen as superior or more legitimate.

The "Western" health films were considered the leading pattern, but their adaptation in Eastern Europe is explored in the book in terms of cultural revision, (re-)interpretation and (re-)creation, highlighting the multiple versions of the cinematic stories.

During the socialist period, Soviet influence became prevalent.

Health films from both East and West were often exported to the then so called developing countries, as part of international aid programs. This export was not an equal exchange but often reflected a form of cultural and informational hegemony, where the exporting countries imposed their health paradigms on the recipient nations.

Health films from Central and Eastern Europe were exported to other countries, particularly within the socialist bloc, but also to the "Third world" which was understood as a practice of socialist solidarity. These films sometimes carried implicit assumptions of superiority, portraying socialist health practices as more advanced compared to those in "developing" societies.

The book explores how health films and the ideologies they propagated were influenced by broader international trends and collaborations. This was evident for example in the use of similar themes and narratives in health films, promoting ideas about hygiene, disease prevention, and the ideal family structure that often had racial undertones.

The structure of the book is not linear and chronological but rather organized around key topics. This thematic approach allows the authors to explore various aspects of health films in depth and from multiple perspectives.

Part 1 "Child and nation in the focus of rescue-mission health films" explores the central role that health films played in promoting the health and welfare of children within the broader context of nation-building and national health campaigns. Children were seen as the future of the nation, making their health and well-being a primary focus of public health initiatives. Health films aimed at children were part of broader efforts to build a strong, healthy population, which was considered essential for the nation's progress and survival. The effectiveness of these films in shaping public attitudes and behaviors towards child health and national duty is discussed. The authors examine how films targeted at improving child health were intertwined with ideologies of national strength and purity, often reflecting eugenic ideas. They reflect on how these films contributed to the normalization of eugenic ideas and the prioritization of national health over individual rights.

Part 2 "Health films for teaching children" delves into the dual role of health films as educational tools and vehicles for broader social and moral education. The primary goal of these films was to teach children about hygiene, nutrition, disease prevention, and healthy lifestyles. By focusing on children, these films sought to shape not only individual health behaviors but also societal values and norms. The authors consider

both the positive impacts, such as improved hygiene practices, and the potential negative effects of embedding eugenic ideologies, subtly promoting concepts of genetic health in educational content, aimed at influencing children's perceptions of health and heredity.

In Part 3 “Men and women in the focus of health films”, the authors explore the portrayal of masculinity and femininity in health films, as well as the intersection of health education and gender ideologies. Films for women often focused on topics like pregnancy, childbirth, and infant care, while films for men addressed issues like workplace safety and physical fitness. Health films often reinforced traditional gender roles, portraying women primarily as caregivers and men as workers and protectors. Health films are interpreted as *Bildungsroman* for teaching men “proper” male behavior, including the prevention of alcoholism and venereal diseases. The influence of eugenic ideas is evident in films dealing with reproductive health, emphasizing the importance of “healthy” reproduction and the prevention of hereditary diseases, and serving as medical surveillance over women.

The final part 4 “Health films for the interwar periphery” the authors devote to the role and impact of health films in the peripheral regions of Central and Eastern Europe during the interwar period. The section discusses the unique public health challenges faced by peripheral and rural areas, such as higher rates of infectious diseases, poor sanitation, and limited access to medical care. Health films were used as a tool to educate these populations about basic health practices and disease prevention. This section emphasizes the importance of understanding the contextual and logistical challenges of public health education in peripheral regions, as well as the critical role of health films in improving health outcomes and promoting social change during the interwar period. It illuminates the dynamics of campaigns against infectious and sexually transmitted diseases as multi-level projects to ensure global health security, dividing the world into “developing” countries, where warnings were to be issued about potential outbreaks of infectious diseases, and the developed countries that were to be protected. Such a model was adopted by Eastern European states to legitimize themselves and the policy of internal colonialism towards their peripheral regions.

Shmidt and Kaser discuss how different health films were tailored to specific audiences. The target audiences for health films were carefully chosen and differentiated based on the specific health issues being addressed, the social and cultural context, and the intended impact of the films. Films for the general public were made to be easily understanda-

ble, often using simple language, visual aids, and dramatizations to convey messages. These films were distributed through public screenings in cinemas, community centers, and even mobile units in rural areas to reach a broad audience. The use of animation, engaging stories, and relatable characters characterized films aimed to capture the attention of younger audiences. Health films became integrated into school curricula and special screenings at schools to ensure that children and adolescents received these messages in an educational setting. Women (especially mothers) were a special target group. Films often included information specifically targeted at mothers, such as breastfeeding, child nutrition, and early childhood development. Such films were screened at women's clubs, community health centers, and other places where women gathered, sometimes followed by discussions led by health professionals. This reflected and reinforced binary gender roles, strengthening the traditional view of women as primary caregivers responsible for the well-being of the family. The focus on maternal responsibility in health education reinforced the idea that nurturing and caregiving are inherently 'natural' female roles. Simultaneously, while many films reinforced traditional roles, some also empowered women by providing them with knowledge and skills that could enhance their autonomy and influence within the household. By educating women on health matters, these films elevated women's status and importance within the family and community, potentially challenging the patriarchal structure in subtle ways. Films targeting healthcare professionals and educators included in some cases women in professional roles, such as nurses and doctors. The representation of women in professional capacities challenged the traditional view of women solely as 'homemakers'. It highlighted their role to contribute to society beyond the domestic sphere.

Shmidt and Kaser's analysis of the authors is intersectional, combining gender, class, religion. Class-based metaphors in health films often depicted a dichotomy between the educated, middle-class families who followed modern health practices and the working-class or rural and Muslim families portrayed as backward or ignorant. This framing served to stigmatize lower-class families while promoting "white" middle-class norms of parenting and hygiene.

The authors cover a diverse range of health films to explore their development and impact in different historical, cultural, and social contexts: Venereal Disease Films (which emerged in the early to mid-20th century, particularly during and after the World Wars when venereal diseases were a significant public health concern), as well as Maternal and

Child Health Films, Hygiene and Sanitation Films, Nutrition and Dietary Films, Mental Health Films, Occupational Health and Safety Films, Alcoholism Abuse and Ant-Smoking Campaigns, Vaccination Campaign Films and others.

Films on tuberculosis serve as one of the ‘case studies’. The book includes a dedicated section – Chapter 13, Part 4, entitled “Films of the National Tuberculosis Association (NTA): Rooting health films for the periphery in the racial hierarchies of the interwar United States”. The NTA played a crucial role in the fight against TB by promoting public health education and advocating for improved sanitary conditions and medical care. The organization produced numerous health films aimed at educating the public about TB prevention and treatment. Shmidt and Kaser demonstrate the contradictory use of health films: while these films played a role in educating the public about TB, they also contributed to the marginalization of racial minorities by depicting them as more susceptible to disease and less capable of adhering to health guidelines. Health films produced by the National Tuberculosis Association during the interwar period were influenced by, but also reinforced, socioeconomic and racial hierarchies prevalent in the United States at the time. The racialized approach to health education had long-term implications for public health efforts and the perception of racial minorities in the United States. And far beyond! Incorporated into the broader analysis of health films, the authors present different TB films from Central and Eastern Europe, providing a nuanced and comprehensive examination of how these films contributed to the fight against tuberculosis while also reflecting the social and cultural contexts in which they were produced.

In light of the topic of the special issue, “Institutional Care”, it is worth noting that Shmidt and Kaser pay special attention to the portrayal of institutionalized childcare. “The institutionalized child as a precondition for the healthy nation” is the revealing title of a subchapter that focuses on interwar films depicting the institutionalized child as a model for a healthy future citizen. These portrayals were intertwined with notions of eugenics and social hygiene, reflecting the era's emphasis on controlling and improving public health through state intervention. Shmidt and Kaser analyze how health films served as tools for promoting specific social policies and ideologies. Health films addressed nations as families in order to include them in the multilevel process of institutionalizing care for children. A number of the films produced in interwar Prague and Zagreb are “rescue” films, designed to convince people of the goodwill of a state that cares for future generations. The neglected child,

the protagonist in each of the films, eventually reaches the best possible position by being placed in an institution.

For example, the book delves into the work of Mladen Širola, a prominent filmmaker, to illustrate how his films aimed to promote the idea of “irresponsible parenting” and its opposite – collective care as a means to improve national health standards, reflecting the broader eugenic and humanistic debates of the interwar period.

The films highlighted the contrast between collective care and traditional family structures, often portraying the latter as backward or inadequate. This dichotomy was used to justify the institutionalization of children, especially those from marginalized communities, such as the Roma, Muslim, or disabled children, which underscored a path dependency in the child protection systems of the region. The conflict between “irresponsible parents” and the paternalistic state is shaped by consistent masculinization: powerful men make decisions, and devoted women implement them.

The move towards deconstructing the idea of the ‘institutionalized child as a precondition for a healthy nation’ and the raising critique on institutional childcare is illustrated by examining films influenced by John Bowlby’s “Attachment Theory” from the 1950s. The films, debating the emotional deprivation of children in residential care, had a significant impact, sparking broader debates and introducing child psychology, stimulating initiatives for developing substitute family care, and strengthening family-, adoption- and foster care policies. The examples given suggest that the popularity of attachment theory in Czechoslovakia only peaked in the early 1960s. At the time, the ‘familialization’ of social policy served several political objectives. In addition to legitimizing the political authority of the then-new President of Czechoslovakia, Antonin Novotny, the main goals mirrored those of attachment theory in Western European states in the previous decade: reducing expenditure on pre-school care by emphasizing the mother’s ‘indispensable role’ in early child development and pushing women out of many labor market roles they had gained access to during the first decade of socialist rule. By following the Czechoslovak film director Kurt Goldberger, highlighting his extensive experience in Great Britain studying British educational films, analyzing his 1963 film “*Deti bez lasky*” [Children Without Love], and noting his emigration after the Warsaw Pact Invasion of Czechoslovakia in 1968 to West Germany where he continued his career as a documentary filmmaker, Schmidt and Kaser open up a wide field for further re-

search on the interconnected world of "traveling" policies, people, ideas, knowledge, and technologies.

Shmidt and Kaser's critical history underscores the complexity of health films as powerful tools for both education and social engineering. By examining the multifaceted roles and impacts of these films, the authors provide valuable insights into the interplay between health education, eugenics, gender norms, and societal change in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond.

The dense analysis of health films is based on a variety of sources from local, national (film) archives, specialised (medical) media and mass media, etc. Films that had not survived as films are also included, reconstructed on the basis of negatives, photographs, reports etc., and the process of their creation and influence is discussed. Victoria Shmidt and Karl Kaser employ the biographical method to analyze leading personalities in film production and health policy (such as Karel Štapfer, Karel Driml, Andrija Štampar, Kurt Goldberger and others). By focusing on the biographies of key figures in health film production and policy, the authors reveal how personal beliefs, experiences, and motivations of these individuals shaped the content and direction of health films.

Shmidt and Kaser's thoughts on the "renaissance in rescue-mission films after 1989" as a significant cultural and political phenomenon are provoking. "Rescue-mission films" refer to a genre that focuses on saving or rehabilitating individuals, particularly children, who are perceived to be in danger or to be disadvantaged. In the context of the post-1989 era, these films highlighted the failures of the socialist system, portraying it as oppressive, ineffective or corrupt. The genre experienced a renaissance as it became a vehicle for articulating criticisms of the socialist past and promoting new political and social ideals. These films frequently depicted socialist-era policies and institutions as harmful or inadequate, thereby questioning the legitimacy of the socialist system as a whole. By highlighting systemic failures, filmmakers sought to discredit the previous regime and to promote the new capitalist order. While the post-1989 rescue-mission films played an important role in criticising the socialist past and promoting new democratic values, their often one-sided perspective can hinder a more nuanced and differentiated understanding of socialist societies. A balanced approach is essential for a comprehensive historical narrative that reflects the complexities of the socialist states within the global world divided by the "Iron Curtain".

In conclusion, the aim of questioning the mode typical of master narratives which consider Eastern European countries as minor actors,

not subjects but impersonal singularities of global politics, is achieved. The “dense description” – of the film subject, of (political) ideas, the interrelations between different genres, the use of motifs and the multi-layered development of the characters, the biographical method applied to leading personalities – makes the book an intriguing read.

Written in a readable style, the book contributes to developing critical thinking (and film viewing), triggering a critical re-examination of narrative practices, and moving towards a more nuanced understanding of public health, gender-based politics and the struggle for social justice. The authors conclude their research with the assertion that “the critical history of health film in Eastern Europe seems like an endless story that must be revisited under the call of new events and actions necessary for deconstructing deeply rooted master narratives concerning the emancipation of former subalterns and ascribing greater historical responsibility to Eastern Europe.” Their primary aim is to stimulate further research, reflecting their mission to encourage ongoing scholarly inquiry.

With their book, Victoria Shmidt and Karl Kaser provide a rich foundation for scholars from various disciplines – including history, social and cultural anthropology, medical anthropology, ethnology, visual studies, cinema research, and critical heritage studies. Their work encourages scholars and broader audiences to embrace and expand upon this understanding, fostering critical thinking and promoting a deeper, more nuanced exploration of health films and their impact on society.